

**ROLE OF PARA SURGICAL PROCEDURE IN ANO RECTAL DISEASES: REVIEW
ARTICLE****Dr. Rohit Baban Jadhav^{*1}, Dr. Amit Ramchandra Shedge² and Dr. Shubhangini Nagralmath³**¹P.G. Scholer, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College and Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.²Professor, HOD, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College and Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.³Professor and GUIDE, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College And Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rohit Baban Jadhav**

P.G. Scholer, Department of PG Studies in Shalyatantra, LRP Ayurvedic Medical College and Reserch Centre Islampur, Sangli.

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ABSTRACT

Shalya Tantra is one of the important branches of Ayurveda in which surgical and parasurgical techniques has described for management of various diseases. parasurgical procedures are minimally invasive techniques used for treating various anorectal diseases. The father of surgery, Sushruta, classified surgery scientifically in a systematic way, and his comprehensive clinical knowledge and management concepts are still relevant today. Anushastra Karma is the term for a surgical treatment carried out without the use of surgical equipment using non-surgical tools or objects. Different Anushastra karma, such as Kshara karma, Kshara Sutra, Agnikarma, Siravyadaha, and Jalukavacharana (leech therapy), were described by Acharya Sushruta for various medical conditions. The Kshara Sutra is used to treat conditions like anal fistula, hemorrhoids, and pilonidal sinus. Kshara Karma involves the direct application of herbal alkaline paste to the affected area. Agnikarma involves the use of a specialized heated metallic rod to cauterize tissue. Raktamokshana refers to various bloodletting techniques that purify the blood by releasing accumulated toxins or "bad blood".

KEYWORD: Parasurgical technique, Anorectal disease, Anushastra Karma, Kshara karma, Kshara Sutra, Agnikarma.**INTRODUCTION**

One of the most significant branches of Ayurveda, the Shalya Tantra, provides descriptions of several surgical and Parasurgical techniques. There are huge numbers of diseases like hemorrhoids, fistula-in-ano etc.^[1] which can effectively be cured using para surgical methods of Ayurveda. These are simple to conduct and withstand, very effective in terms of cost and benefits. Para surgical procedures have been indicated for different diseases that cannot be cured by any medication or where surgery is not possible to treat the condition or there is great chance of recurrence of disease. Para surgical methods are effective, easy to apply in the management of many roga also, easy to perform, less chance of recurrence, sutureless, less post-operative hemorrhage and minimal pain. The purpose of this review is to evaluate and

discuss the utility and probable mode of action of para surgical procedures used in different Ano rectal diseases in a scientific manner.

Acharya Sushruta explained 15 different types of Anushastras. Those are Twaksara (Bamboo Bark), Spatika, Kancha (glass), Kuruvind, Jalauka (Leeches), Agni(flame), Kshara(Alkali), Nakha (Nails), Goji, Shefalika Shaka-patera, Kareera, Bala(Hair), Anguli(finger).^[2] It is indicated in childrens, sensitive or fearful persons and in absence of surgical instruments. These Karmas are minimally invasive. The parasurgical procedures are the marvels of Shalya practice and they can be carried out with minimal discomfort to the patients. It is gaining popularity in modern times because of their effectiveness in treating chronic diseases.^[3]

1) Kshar sutra

It is a specific method used to treat many anal disorders, including piles and fistula. A medicated thread composed of natural herbs and alkaline compounds is used in the process to help heal the damage tissues. The medications utilized in this therapy also have analgesic and anti-inflammatory characteristics.

2) Kshar karma

Using medicated alkaline paste (kshara) to eliminate harmful tissue and promote wound healing is known as ksharakarma. Fissures, piles, and fistulas are among the conditions for which it can be applied. The paste has a cauterizing action and is made from medicinal plants.

3) Agni karma^[4]

Through the use of different materials, agni is applied either directly or indirectly to treat diseases in agnikarma. It is referenced under Ashtavidha Shastra Karma in Sushruta's texts.^[5] Agnikarma as one of the 36 Upakramas (therapeutic procedures) for treating wounds, specifically under the category of Dwi-Vraniya Chikitsa.^[6] Agnikarma includes any procedure that directly or indirectly involves the agni. Agnikarma prevents diseases from recurring once they have been cured. Agnikarma has the effect of sterilization. It kills bacteria due to its heat impact. Thus, post-agnikarma wounds are rarely infected. Agnikarma is indicated disorders of Asthi (bone), Sandhi (joint) and Snayu (ligament/tendon) also in Arsha (Piles), Arbuda (tumour), Bhagandar (Fistula in ano), Sira- Snayu-Asthi-Sandhigata Vata Vikaras (Ligament injury, Tendonitis, joint pains) and Gridhrasi (Sciatic).

4) Kshar varti

This treatment involves inserting a medicated plug (*varti*) made from alkaline substances into abscess cavities or sinus tracts. It helps in the debridement of fibrous and necrotic tissue. It is used in pilonidal sinus and fistula in ano.

Role Of Parasurgical Procedure In Ano Rectal Diseases

1) Fissure in Ano^[7,8]

Parikartika is one of the most common Ano rectal Disease. It is longitudinal tear in the lower end of anus. It is the most painful condition affecting the anal region. Sometimes a little tag, swelling of the skin develops at the edge of the anus. This is called as sentinel tag or Sentinel Piles. This stays even after the fissure heals unless excised. It commonly seen in young & middle age people. Due to wrong food habits fissures are found in children also.

❖ Symptoms

- Severe burning – cutting pain during and after passing stool
- Severe constipation
- Drop of blood or streak of fresh blood during defecation.

- Sentinel piles (Tag of skin at the outer end of anus)
- Itching
- Hard stool

❖ Causes

- Extreme condition like severe constipation or dysentery
- Surgeries (Piles surgery)
- Sphincter hypertonia (spasm of anus)
- Repeated child birth
- Excessive use of ointments
- Excessive use of laxatives

❖ Use of parasurgical method – Agnikarma

This is para surgical procedure. This is a sort of thermal cauterisation.

In this procedure sentinel tags are removed by thermal cauterisation and sphincterotomy also will be performed by agnikarma to reduce spasm of anal ring.

2) Fistula In Ano (Bhagandara)^[9]

Anal Fistula is an abnormal tube like passage (communication) between the interior of the anal canal (or rectum) and the outer skin surface around the anus. One opening of the fistula (Internal opening) is inside the anus (or rectum) and another opening (External opening) is on skin surface around the anus. A tube like structure (Fistula track) connect them.

❖ Symptoms of fistula

- Persistent seropurulent (sticky) discharge of pus and/or stool from the external opening near anus
- History of recurrent swelling & abscess on buttock
- Itching & moist feeling in the anal area
- Pain in the lump on buttock
- Flatus (gas) escape from external skin opening

❖ Causes of fistula

- Ignored fissure can get infected and get converted in to fistula
- Spicy & fast food habits, sitting job
- Can cause as a complication in Abscess, Tuberculosis.(T.B), Cancer, IBS (Inflammatory bowel Syndrome), Ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease

❖ Use of parasurgical method – Kshar sutra

Kshara-sutra treatment is a well accepted Ayurvedic technique for treating Fistula-in-Ano

Advantage of kshara sutra is

- 1) Minimal recurrence
- 2) Minimal hospital stay
- 3) Non invasive technique
- 4) Patient can resume day today activities soon
- 5) Less complication. (chances of incontinence is rare in this procedure)

Kshara Sutra Procedure

Probing is done through a malleable probe to locate the

internal opening.

If internal opening is located, the probe is pushed out through the anal verge and the track is threaded loosely by Kshara sutra.

3) Pilonidal Sinus (Nadivrana)

'Pilonidal' means nest of hairs. A pilonidal sinus is a tube like random shape structure which contains a tuft of hairs. This cyst / abscess with infected tissues, pus, blood is found under the skin covering the last part of back bone – tail bone between the buttocks. It is also called as "Jeep- Bottom" or Barber's disease because this is very common in Jeep drivers.

❖ Symptoms of pilonidal sinus

- Pus discharge from the lump on lower back
- History of recurrent swelling & abscess on lower back
- Fever, pain

❖ Causes of pilonidal sinus

- A job involving a lot of sitting (a sedentary occupation)
- Being overweight (obesity)
- A previous persistent irritation or injury to the affected area
- Having a hairy, deep natal cleft
- A family history of the condition

❖ Use of parasurgical method – Kshar sutra

Pilonidal sinus treated by Ksharsutra treatment. This treatment is the best alternative for modern surgery techniques. Ksharsutra treatment is now replacing all complex surgeries for pilonidal sinus with great success rate.

Using appropriate technique kshar sutra is inserted correctly in the pilonidal sinus. This herbal thread is changed after every 7 days. The duration of the treatment depend on the length & stage of pilonidal cyst. No recurrence, no daily dressing required, no hospitalization required, no bed rest and patient can resume his / her routine work within few hours.

4) Haemorrhoids (piles)^[10]

Haemorrhoids also called piles, it is a dilation of the veins in the haemorrhoidal plexus with submucosal tissue consist of venule, arteriole, and fine muscle fiber located in the anal canal.

Haemorrhoid derived from two Greek word Heam – Blood, Rhoos – Flow

❖ Symptoms of piles

- Bleeding (Splash in the pan)
- No pain
- Prolapsed mass through anus
- Discharge of mucous (Sticky fluid)
- Itching

❖ Causes of piles

- Chronic Constipation
- Straining during passing stool
- Genetic or Hereditary
- Straining during child birth
- Repeated diarrhea – dysentery
- Continues sitting or standing work position
- Continues Lifting heavy weights
- Habit to suppress the urge of defecation

❖ Types of Piles

As per the site

- External – when thrombosed, cause severe pain
- Internal – may have painless bleeding
- Interno-external

According to length

- First degree piles : No mass protruding from the anus(Only bleeding)
- Second degree piles : Piles mass protrudes out from the anus but returns spontaneously after passing stool
- Third degree piles: Piles mass protrudes out from the anus but some force (with finger) require to push back
- Fourth degree piles : Piles mass remains protruded out of anus permanent

❖ Use of parasurgical method – Ksharkarma^[11]

It is non surgical procedure. A medicine derived from various herbs (called 'KSHAR') is applied on pile mass. Kshar reduceses & shrinks piles. It is a type of chemical cauterization. Patient need to take rest at home for a period of 7 to 14 days.

CONCLUSION

Parasurgical procedures is equally important as surgical practice in Shastrakarma. It is an important part of Ayurveda. All these karmas are widely used on day to day to cure various ano rectal diseases with good results. It is an ambulatory treatment modality and affordable to common man as it is very cost effective. Post- procedure complication are also minimal or negligible. It is indicated in childrens, sensitive or fearful persons and in absence of surgical instruments. These Karmas are minimally invasive. The parasurgical procedures are the marvels of Shalya practice and they can be carried out with minimal discomfort to the patients. It is gaining popularity in modern times because of their effectiveness in treating diseases.

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